

BIAXIAL STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS
OF FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINAE*

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced composite laminae have three independent strengths, X , Y , and S (maximum normal stress parallel to the fibers of a unidirectionally fiber-reinforced lamina, maximum normal stress perpendicular to the fibers, and maximum shearing stress in principal material coordinates). These strengths can also be used to characterize laminae with fibers in both of two orthogonal directions in the plane of the lamina (a more comprehensive set of strengths is necessary to characterize anisotropic laminae, i.e., with fibers in more than the two orthogonal directions). Several different types of off-axis strength behavior result for various relative values of the independent strengths. For example, the shearing strength could be high relative to certain values of X and Y leading to a special type of strength versus off-axis angle of loading behavior. Or, S could be low relative to those values of X and Y leading to yet another type of strength versus angle of loading behavior.

The biaxial strength characteristics of two composite materials failure theories, the Tsai-Hill theory and the Tsai-Wu theory, are examined in this paper. The principles of the maxima and minima of a function of a single variable are used to determine the various relations between the strengths that lead to various distinctly different behaviors for strength in other than principal material directions. For both failure criteria, the biaxial behavior is determined for off-axis normal stress as well as shearing stress in coordinates at some angle to the principal material directions.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite materials do not have a single strength as do homogeneous isotropic materials. Instead, strength is a function of load direction relative to the fiber reinforcement directions. For unidirectionally oriented fiber reinforcement in a plane the independent strengths are X , Y , and S , the maximum normal stress parallel to the fibers, the maximum normal stress perpendicular to the fibers, and the maximum shearing stress in principal material coordinates, respectively, as in Fig. 1. Note that X and Y are generally different under tension loading than under compression loading, but S is the same irrespective of the sign of the applied shear stress. For composites with fibers in more than one direction (excluding composites made of

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FIGURE 1 STRENGTHS IN PRINCIPAL MATERIAL DIRECTIONS

layers of unidirectional reinforcement), the same names (X, Y, and S) can be used, but they do not have the same meaning relative to the now nonexistent single fiber direction. Instead, a rather obvious association with identifiable principal material directions can be made for orthogonally oriented fibers or with other convenient directions for nonorthogonally oriented fibers. In these cases, more independent strength parameters than X, Y, and S are often essential, and even the shear strengths can be different when the sign of the applied shear stress is reversed. We concentrate in this paper on the simplest case of unidirectionally reinforced composite laminae (the analysis for which can be extended to the more general cases without great difficulty).

After the basic material strengths X, Y, and S (or X_t , X_c , Y_t , Y_c , and S if necessary) are measured, the following question arises: What is the strength under uniaxial loading at some angle to the fiber direction, i.e., what is $\sigma_{x_{max}}$ in Fig. 2? Or, what is $\tau_{xy_{max}}$ in Fig. 2? To answer these

FIGURE 2
OFF-AXIS NORMAL AND
SHEAR LOADING

questions, we could measure the strength for many values of θ . For design purposes, however, we need that information expressed in the convenient mathematical relationship of a strength theory. The development of such a strength theory is presumed to have taken place before the topics of interest in this paper.

Our objective in this paper is to study the biaxial strength characteristics of fiber-reinforced composite materials as represented with various failure theories such as the Tsai-Hill [1] and Tsai-Wu [2] failure theories. This study is conducted by examining the physical consequences on the off-axis strength of unidirectionally reinforced composites because of having

various combinations of ranges of values of X , Y , and S . First, we review the basic mathematical concepts that are essential to the study, i.e., how to determine the maxima and minima of the off-axis strengths. Then, we apply the concepts to the Tsai-Hill failure theory for off-axis normal strength and off-axis shear strength and interpret the results. Finally, we do the same for the Tsai-Wu failure theory.

The basic procedure for off-axis strength prediction is analogous to the off-axis stiffness prediction analysis of Jones [3]. With both the off-axis strength and stiffness prediction tools, we can expect to perform initial evaluations of potential composite materials without the expense of off-axis tests. Of course, such off-axis tests will be necessary as a material passes from the class of a possible material to a soon to be used material. Also, in design studies, the relative merits of several materials can be measured to some extent by their off-axis characteristics which can be quantified by use of the present analysis.

MAXIMA AND MINIMA OF STRENGTH

The basic problem is to determine the loads at which fiber-reinforced composite materials fail when loaded in coordinates at some angle θ to the principal material directions in which the characteristic strengths X , Y , and S are known. We will first express the criteria for off-axis normal and shear strengths in terms of the off-axis loading angle and the characteristic principal material direction strengths. Then, we seek the angles at which the maximum and minimum strength values occur. The mathematical problem is to find the maxima, minima, and inflection points of a function f (the off-axis strength) of a single variable θ (the off-axis loading angle).

The general procedure for this advanced calculus problem is given by Jones [4]. He shows that the character of the derivatives of higher order than the second must sometimes be known in order to determine whether a stationary value is a maximum, minimum, or inflection point. Basically, a stationary value occurs wherever the curve has a horizontal tangent as in Fig. 3. If the

FIGURE 3

MAXIMA AND MINIMA OF A FUNCTION, f

lowest order nonzero derivative is negative and of even order, the stationary point is a maximum as at θ_3 . If the lowest order nonzero derivative is positive and of even order, the stationary point is a minimum as at θ_1 . However, if the lowest order nonzero derivative is odd, then the stationary point is an inflection point as at θ_2 . Thus, we merely evaluate higher and higher order derivatives at stationary values until we find a nonzero derivative and from it determine the character of the stationary point. We will use this mathematical tool in the subsequent sections.

APPLICATION TO TSAI-HILL FAILURE CRITERION

The Tsai-Hill failure criterion for biaxial loading in the plane of a unidirectionally reinforced composite (the 1-2 plane, where the 1-direction is the fiber direction and the 2-direction is perpendicular to the fibers but in their plane) is [1]

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X^2} - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{X^2} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where the stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , and τ_{12} are applied in principal material directions. This criterion will be reexpressed for off-axis normal loading and off-axis shear loading in the following sections. Then, the maximum and minimum values of off-axis normal and shear strengths will be found.

OFF-AXIS NORMAL STRENGTH

When a unidirectionally reinforced composite is loaded with a uniaxial stress σ_x at angle θ to the fiber direction as in Fig. 2, the stresses in the principal material directions are

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_x \cos^2 \theta \quad \sigma_2 = \sigma_x \sin^2 \theta \quad \tau_{12} = -\sigma_x \sin \theta \cos \theta \quad (2)$$

Thus, the Tsai-Hill failure criterion for this loading can be written as

$$\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{X^2} + \left(\frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{1}{X^2} \right) \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{Y^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_x^2} \quad (3)$$

which is an expression for σ_x as a function of off-axis loading angle θ and the independent material strengths, X , Y , and S . We seek the largest and smallest values of σ_x as a function of θ in accordance with the principles stated in the section MAXIMA AND MINIMA OF STRENGTH.

Equation (3) is actually expressed in terms of $1/\sigma_x^2$ and can be multiplied by $(XYS)^2$ to obtain

$$\left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 = Y^2 S^2 \cos^4 \theta + Y^2 (X^2 - S^2) \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta + X^2 S^2 \sin^4 \theta \quad (4)$$

from which we seek the extrema of $(XYS/\sigma_x)^2$ as a function of θ . The minima of this quantity coincide with the maxima of σ_x ; similarly, the maxima of $(XYS/\sigma_x)^2$ coincide with the minima of σ_x .

First, we differentiate Eq. (4):

$$\frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 = A \sin \theta \cos^3 \theta + B \sin^3 \theta \cos \theta \quad (5)$$

where

$$A = 2Y^2(X^2 - 3S^2) \quad B = 2(2X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2 + Y^2S^2) \quad (6)$$

Extrema of Eq. (4) occur when its first derivative is zero, i.e., when Eq. (5) is zero, or

$$\sin \theta \cos \theta (A \cos^2 \theta + B \sin^2 \theta) = 0 \quad (7)$$

The solutions of Eq. (7) are

$$\begin{array}{lll} \sin \theta_1 = 0 & \text{or} & \theta_1 = 0^\circ \\ \cos \theta_2 = 0 & \text{or} & \theta_2 = 90^\circ \\ A \cos^2 \theta_3 + B \sin^2 \theta_3 = 0 & \text{or} & \tan \theta_3 = \sqrt{-A/B} \end{array} \quad (8)$$

The value of θ_3 obviously depends on the values of A and B which in turn depend on X, Y, and S. We are interested in θ_3 between 0° and 90° where $\tan\theta_3$ is positive. Thus, either

$$A < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad B > 0$$

or

$$A > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad B < 0$$

For $A < 0$ and $B > 0$, the most stringent of the two conditions is

$$S > \frac{X}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (9)$$

For $A > 0$ and $B < 0$, the most stringent condition is

$$S < \frac{XY}{\sqrt{2X^2 + Y^2}} \quad (10)$$

At this point, we conclude that σ_x achieves a stationary value when S satisfies either of the bounds in Eqs. (9) and (10) (and at $\theta_1 = 0^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$ irrespective of the value of S). In order to determine whether θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 correspond to maxima, minima, or inflection points of $\sigma_x(\theta)$, the higher order derivatives of $(XYS/\sigma_x)^2$ must be examined. Those derivatives are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2}{d\theta^2} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 &= A(-3\cos^2\theta + 4\cos^4\theta) + B(-1 + 5\cos^2\theta - 4\cos^4\theta) \\ \frac{d^3}{d\theta^3} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 &= [A(6 - 16\cos^2\theta) + B(-10 + 16\cos^2\theta)]\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ \frac{d^4}{d\theta^4} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 &= A(-6 + 60\cos^2\theta - 64\cos^4\theta) + B(10 - 68\cos^2\theta + 64\cos^4\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Note that all derivatives are expressed in terms of powers of $\cos\theta$. This form is especially useful for examination of the character of the root at θ_3 because the last part of Eq. (8) can be expressed as

$$\cos\theta_3 = \sqrt{\frac{-B}{A-B}} \quad (12)$$

and, hence, ready substitution of Eq. (12) in Eqs. (11) is possible.

At $\theta_1 = 0^\circ$, the second derivative is merely A. Thus, if $A > 0$, then σ_x is a maximum. If $A < 0$, then σ_x is a minimum at 0° . If A is zero, we must appeal to the third derivative which is identically zero. Thus, we appeal to the fourth derivative:

$$\left. \frac{d^4}{d\theta^4} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 \right|_{\theta_1=0^\circ} = 6B = 12(2X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2 + Y^2S^2) \quad (13)$$

But $A = 0$, so $S^2 = X^2/3$ from Eq. (6), and Eq. (13) becomes

$$\left. \frac{d^4}{d\theta^4} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 \right|_{\theta_1=0^\circ} = \frac{2}{3} X^2(X^2 - Y^2) \quad (14)$$

which is always positive because a unidirectional composite is stronger in the fiber direction than perpendicular to the fibers, i.e., $X > Y$. Thus, the first nonzero derivative is even, so σ_x is a maximum. Finally,

$$\text{At } 0^\circ \begin{cases} \sigma_x \text{ is maximum for } S \leq X/\sqrt{3} \\ \sigma_x \text{ is minimum for } S > X/\sqrt{3} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

At $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$, the second derivative is $-B$. Thus, if $B < 0$, then σ_x is a maximum. If $B > 0$, then σ_x is a minimum. If $B = 0$, then we investigate the derivatives and find that the fourth derivative is negative, so σ_x is a minimum. Finally,

$$\text{At } \theta_2 = 90^\circ \begin{cases} \sigma_x \text{ is a maximum for } S < \frac{XY}{\sqrt{2X^2 + Y^2}} \\ \sigma_x \text{ is a minimum for } S \geq \frac{XY}{\sqrt{2X^2 + Y^2}} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

At θ_3 , the analysis is simpler in that only the second derivative must be evaluated:

$$\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2} \left(\frac{XYS}{\sigma_x} \right)^2 = \frac{2AB}{A - B} \quad (17)$$

For low S , i.e., $S < XY/\sqrt{2X^2 + Y^2}$, $A > 0$ and $B < 0$ and $A - B$ can also be shown to be positive, so the second derivative is negative; thus, σ_x is a minimum. For high S , i.e., $S > X/\sqrt{3}$, $A < 0$ and $B > 0$ with $A - B < 0$, so the second derivative is positive, and σ_x is a maximum. We determine what happens when $S = X/\sqrt{3}$ and $S = XY/\sqrt{2X^2 + Y^2}$ by observing the behavior for those values of S at $\theta_1 = 0^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$. That is, σ_x is a minimum at 0° and 90° for $S = X/\sqrt{3}$; then σ_x must achieve a maximum between those minima. Also, σ_x is a maximum at 0° and 90° when $S = XY/\sqrt{2X^2 + Y^2}$, so σ_x must achieve a minimum between those maxima.

The possible off-axis strength behavior is shown schematically in Fig. 4 for the three ranges of S : low, medium, and high. The obvious conclusions from this analysis are that unidirectional composites have off-axis strengths that are greater than X if S is high enough, some that are less than Y if S is low enough, and some that are bounded by X and Y . The key parameter in determining the type of off-axis behavior is the value of the shear strength relative to X and Y . Shear strength is ordinarily thought of as being dependent on tensile strength of isotropic materials. However, for fiber-reinforced composites, shear strength is independent of all other strengths. Thus, composites can have the types of behavior exhibited in Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4 OFF-AXIS NORMAL STRENGTH FOR TSAI-HILL FAILURE CRITERION

(a) Low S

(b) Medium S

(c) High S

FIGURE 5

VARIATION OF σ_x WITH θ
FOR LOW, MEDIUM, AND HIGH
SHEAR STRENGTH

Another way of looking at the off-axis strength is in the form of a polar plot, as in Fig. 5. There, for equal strengths in tension and compression, the off-axis strength is plotted radially versus the angle of loading which is plotted circumferentially. The diagrams for low, medium, and high shear strength are all symmetric relative to the principal material directions, i.e., symmetric about the 1 and 2 axes. However, unlike our usual interpretation of principal values such as principal stresses, the maximum and minimum strengths do not necessarily occur in those principal directions! Thus, the concept of principal material directions must be restricted to axes of material property symmetry, not directions of largest or smallest material properties. Thus, for high S, the largest strength occurs in four directions, and each strength is greater than X. For low S, the least strength occurs in four directions, and each strength is lower than Y. For medium values of S, only two maximum and two minimum strengths occur, and they are in principal material directions. As an aside, the maximum off-axis strength might not coincide with the maximum off-axis stiffness so there are additional complications in the complete analysis of a lamina.

Yet another twist on the strength behavior of fiber-reinforced composites is that they often have different strengths in tension than in compression, i.e., $X_t \neq X_c$ and $Y_t \neq Y_c$. The effect of these differences is to skew, sometimes drastically, the appearance of Figs. 5. However, the only computational difficulty we encounter with the Tsai-Hill failure criterion is that we use

different values of X and Y depending on the sign of the stresses in the principal material direction. That is, we use the same criterion but with different numbers in each quadrant of loading.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES - OFF-AXIS STRENGTH

Composite materials do, in fact, exhibit the types of behavior represented in Fig. 4. A high value of S could be obtained through some reinforcement or lamination scheme. Generally, however, high S composites are not common. Typical strengths for four unidirectionally reinforced composites are listed in Table 1. The strength data are separated into tensile strengths and compressive strengths, so we apply the criteria for low, medium, and high shear

TABLE 1
STRENGTHS OF TYPICAL UNIDIRECTIONALLY REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

PROPERTY	MATERIAL			
	GLASS-EPOXY	BORON-EPOXY	GRAPHITE-EPOXY	KEVLAR-49
X_t	$150 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$200 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$150 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$200 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$
Y_t	$4 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$12 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$6 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$4 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$
S	$6 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$18 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$10 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$6.4 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$
X_c	$150 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$400 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$100 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$40 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$
Y_c	$20 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$40 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$17 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$	$20 \times 10^3 \text{ psi}$

strengths quadrant by quadrant. However, we are interested only in off-axis tensile strength or compressive strength, so we are concerned with only two quadrants, one in which X_t and Y_t are excited and one in which X_c and Y_c are excited. After applying the criteria for whether S is low, medium, or high in Fig. 4, we find that all four materials have a medium S for off-axis tensile strength, but a low S for off-axis compressive strength. Thus, the off-axis compressive strength is lower than Y, the strength perpendicular to the fibers.

We note that low values of Y are generally a weakness of fiber-reinforced composites, so we have identified yet another potential weakness which could actually be regarded as an enhancement of an already present weakness. Accordingly, we must be aware of this fact during design of composite structures so we can generate a design in which this weakness is remedied by means of some lamination scheme.

OFF-AXIS SHEAR STRENGTH

When a unidirectionally reinforced composite is loaded with a shearing stress τ_{xy} in coordinates at angle θ to the principal material coordinates as in Fig. 2, the stresses in principal material directions are:

$$\sigma_1 = 2\tau_{xy} \sin\theta \cos\theta \quad \sigma_2 = -2\tau_{xy} \sin\theta \cos\theta \quad \tau_{12} = \tau_{xy} (\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta) \quad (18)$$

Accordingly, the Tsai-Hill failure criterion, Eq. (1), can be written for this loading as

$$4 \left(\frac{2}{X^2} + \frac{1}{Y^2} - \frac{1}{S^2} \right) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta + \frac{1}{S^2} = \frac{1}{\tau_{xy}^2} \quad (19)$$

which is an expression for off-axis shear strength τ_{xy} as a function of off-axis loading angle θ and the independent material strengths, X , Y , and S . As for off-axis normal strength, we seek the largest and smallest values of τ_{xy} as a function of θ . We first rewrite Eq. (19) by multiplying by $(XYS)^2$ to obtain

$$4(2Y^2S^2 + X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2)\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta + X^2Y^2 = \left(\frac{XYS}{\tau_{xy}}\right)^2 \quad (20)$$

from which we seek the extrema of $(XYS/\tau_{xy})^2$ as a function of θ . First, we differentiate Eq. (20):

$$\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{XYS}{\tau_{xy}}\right)^2 = 8(2Y^2S^2 + X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2)\sin\theta\cos\theta(\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta) \quad (21)$$

Thus, the extrema of $(XYS/\tau_{xy})^2$, which are the zeros of Eq. (21), are

$$\begin{aligned} \sin\theta_1 &= 0 & \text{or} & & \theta_1 &= 0^\circ \\ \cos\theta_2 &= 0 & \text{or} & & \theta_2 &= 90^\circ \\ \sin^2\theta_3 &= \cos^2\theta_3 & \text{or} & & \theta_3 &= 45^\circ \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

No other extrema exist, especially any that are dependent in location on values of the material properties.

To determine the character of the extrema in Eq. (22), we examine the second derivative of the strength criterion, Eq. (20):

$$\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2}\left(\frac{XYS}{\tau_{xy}}\right)^2 = 8(2Y^2S^2 + X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2)(\cos^4\theta - 6\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta + \sin^4\theta) \quad (23)$$

At $\theta_1 = 0^\circ$,

$$\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2}\left(\frac{XYS}{\tau_{xy}}\right)^2 = 8(2Y^2S^2 + X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2) \quad (24)$$

from which we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } 0^\circ \quad \tau_{xy} & \text{ is maximum for } S > \frac{XY}{\sqrt{X^2 + 2Y^2}} \\ \tau_{xy} & \text{ is minimum for } S < \frac{XY}{\sqrt{X^2 + 2Y^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

These same conclusions are applicable at $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$ because τ_{xy} at 0° is equal to τ_{xy} at 90° . At 45° , the second derivative, Eq. (23), becomes

$$\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2}\left(\frac{XYS}{\tau_{xy}}\right)^2 = -4(2Y^2S^2 + X^2S^2 - X^2Y^2) \quad (26)$$

from which we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } 45^\circ \quad \tau_{xy} & \text{ is maximum for } S < \frac{XY}{\sqrt{X^2 + 2Y^2}} \\ \tau_{xy} & \text{ is minimum for } S > \frac{XY}{\sqrt{X^2 + 2Y^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

We see easily that τ_{xy} is a constant value of S when $S = XY/(X^2 + 2Y^2)^{1/2}$.

Now, the question arises of what to do when the strengths in compression are not equal to those in tension. We must determine which of X_t , X_c , Y_t , or Y_c affect τ_{xy} . We make that determination on the basis of the signs of the normal stresses in principal material directions. For example, when $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$, as in Fig. 2, the normal stress in the fiber direction is tensile, whereas the normal stress transverse to the fibers is compressive. Hence, X_t and Y_c are used in the failure criterion. Similarly, when $-45^\circ < \theta < 0^\circ$, as in Fig. 2, the normal stress in the fiber direction is compressive, and the normal stress transverse to the fibers is tensile, so X_c and Y_t are used in the failure criterion.

The results of the off-axis strength analysis are summarized graphically in Fig. 6. There, four distinctly different types of behavior are possible, depending on the relation of the shear strength to the fiber and transverse

FIGURE 6 OFF-AXIS SHEAR STRENGTH FOR TSAI-HILL FAILURE CRITERION

direction strengths. If the shear strength is lower than the special combination of X and Y in Eqs. (27), then the least shear strength occurs in principal material coordinates. On the other hand, if S is higher than the same combination of X and Y , the greatest shear strength occurs in principal material coordinates, and we must make sure we have enough shear strength in the other loading cases.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES - OFF-AXIS SHEAR STRENGTH

Unidirectional composites have either high shear strength or low shear strength in principal material coordinates insofar as the off-axis shear strength is concerned. If S is less than $X_t Y_c / (X_t^2 + 2Y_c^2)^{1/2}$, then S is the lowest shear strength for $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$. On the other hand, if S is greater than $X_t Y_c / (X_t^2 + 2Y_c^2)^{1/2}$, then S is the highest shear strength for $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$. Similar observations can be made for $-45^\circ < \theta < 0^\circ$, and those observations are identical to the ones for $0^\circ < \theta < 45^\circ$ if the strengths in tension and compression are equal. However, composite materials generally have different strengths in tension and compression. Hence, the possibility exists that the off-axis shear strength is greater than S for $\theta > 0^\circ$ and less than S for $\theta < 0^\circ$.

We examine the off-axis shear strength characteristics of the four example unidirectionally reinforced composite materials in Table 1. When we apply the criteria displayed in Fig. 6, we find that the off-axis shear strength is greater than S for $\theta > 0^\circ$ and less than S for $\theta < 0^\circ$ for all four materials. Thus, even though we recognize that the shear strength is a potential weakness

of composite materials, we must design around an enhancement of this weakness in off-axis shear loading by means of some lamination scheme.

APPLICATION TO TSAI-WU FAILURE CRITERION

The Tsai-Wu failure criterion for biaxial loading in the plane of a unidirectionally reinforced composite is [2]

$$F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_6\tau_{12} + F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 = 1 \quad (28)$$

where F_1 , F_2 , and F_6 are components of a second order tensor and F_{11} , F_{22} , F_{12} , and F_{66} are components of a fourth order tensor, both of which are functions of the strengths in the 1-2 plane. Because of the linear stress terms in Eq. (28), we can treat both tension and compression strength behavior simultaneously, i.e., with one equation, rather than having to piece together several solutions in the four quadrants as for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion. The components of the strength tensors are related to the strengths in tension and compression as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= \frac{1}{X_t} + \frac{1}{X_c} & F_2 &= \frac{1}{Y_t} + \frac{1}{Y_c} & F_6 &= 0 \\ F_{11} &= -\frac{1}{X_t X_c} & F_{22} &= -\frac{1}{Y_t Y_c} & F_{66} &= \frac{1}{S^2} \\ F_{12} &= \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \left[1 - \left(\frac{1}{X_t} + \frac{1}{X_c} + \frac{1}{Y_t} + \frac{1}{Y_c} \right) \sigma + \left(\frac{1}{X_t X_c} + \frac{1}{Y_t Y_c} \right) \sigma^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where σ is the failure stress under equal biaxial tension. Thus, the Tsai-Wu tensor theory has one more strength component than the Tsai-Hill theory, and this component must be measured in a special test (the equal biaxial stress failure test). The failure criterion in Eq. (28) will be reexpressed for off-axis normal and shear loadings in the following sections. Then, the maximum and minimum values of off-axis normal and shear strengths will be found.

OFF-AXIS NORMAL STRENGTH

We substitute the stresses in principal material directions in terms of the uniaxial off-axis stress σ_x , Eq. (2), in the Tsai-Wu criterion, Eq. (28), to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} F_1\sigma_x \cos^2\theta + F_2\sigma_x \sin^2\theta + F_{11}\sigma_x^2 \cos^4\theta + F_{22}\sigma_x^2 \sin^4\theta + F_{66} \frac{2}{x} \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta + \\ + 2F_{12} \frac{2}{x} \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

or, upon gathering coefficients of σ_x and σ_x^2 , we have

$$C\sigma_x^2 + D\sigma_x - 1 = 0 \quad (31)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C &= F_{11}\cos^4\theta + (F_{66} + 2F_{12})\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta + F_{22}\sin^4\theta \\ D &= F_1\cos^2\theta + F_2\sin^2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The direct determination of extrema of a quadratic function such as Eq. (31) (a function of both σ_x and σ_x^2 , in contrast to the Tsai-Hill criterion, Eq. (3), which is a function of σ_x^2 alone) is algebraically difficult if not impossible because of the awkward radicals involved. We take an equally

valid, but simpler, indirect approach and differentiate Eq. (31):

$$C'\sigma_x^2 + 2C\sigma_x\sigma_x' + D'\sigma_x + D\sigma_x' = 0 \quad (33)$$

However, at an extremum, $\sigma_x' = 0$, so

$$\sigma_x(C'\sigma_x + D') = 0 \quad (34)$$

but σ_x is never zero, so

$$C'\sigma_x + D' = 0 \quad (35)$$

but from Eq. (32),

$$\begin{aligned} C' &= -4F_{11}\cos^3\theta\sin\theta + (F_{66} + 2F_{12})(2\sin\theta\cos^3\theta - 2\sin^3\theta\cos\theta) + 4F_{22}\sin^3\theta\cos\theta \\ &= 2\sin\theta\cos\theta[-2F_{11}\cos^2\theta + (F_{66} + 2F_{12})(\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta) + 2F_{22}\sin^2\theta] \quad (36) \end{aligned}$$

$$D' = -2F_1\cos\theta\sin\theta + 2F_2\sin\theta\cos\theta = 2(F_2 - F_1)\sin\theta\cos\theta$$

We observe that Eq. (35) is of the form

$$\sin\theta\cos\theta[f(\theta)\sigma_x + g(\theta)] = 0 \quad (37)$$

Thus, the roots of this equation where σ_x' is zero are

$$\begin{aligned} \sin\theta_1 &= 0 & \text{or} & & \theta_1 &= 0^\circ \\ \cos\theta_2 &= 0 & \text{or} & & \theta_2 &= 90^\circ \\ f(\theta_3)\sigma_x(\theta_3) + g(\theta_3) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

The first two roots are easy to find, but the third root has not been found because of algebraic difficulties encountered when the radicals associated with the solution of Eq. (31) for σ_x are substituted. Instead, we merely recognize that a third root θ_3 can exist (as it does for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion) and examine the behavior of $\sigma_x(\theta)$ at θ_1 and θ_2 to deduce the behavior at θ_3 .

We need to determine σ_x'' to characterize the behavior of σ_x . First, we differentiate Eq. (33),

$$\begin{aligned} C''\sigma_x^2 + 2C'\sigma_x\sigma_x' + 2C'\sigma_x\sigma_x' + 2C(\sigma_x')^2 + 2C\sigma_x\sigma_x'' + D''\sigma_x + D'\sigma_x' \\ + D'\sigma_x' + D\sigma_x'' = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

recognize that $\sigma_x' = 0$, and solve for σ_x'' :

$$\sigma_x'' \Big|_{\sigma_x'=0} = -\sigma_x \frac{C''\sigma_x + D''}{2C\sigma_x + D} \quad (40)$$

where C and D are defined in Eq. (32) and

$$\begin{aligned} C'' &= 12F_{11}\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta - 4F_{11}\cos^4\theta + 12F_{22}\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta - 4F_{22}\sin^4\theta \\ &\quad + 2(F_{66} + 2F_{12})(\cos^4\theta - 6\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta + \sin^4\theta) \\ D'' &= 2(F_2 - F_1)(\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

We are now able to evaluate σ_x'' at the two known roots of Eq. (35).

At $\theta_1 = 0$, we have two possible values of σ_x : $\sigma_x = X_t$ and $\sigma_x = X_c$. First,

$$\sigma_x'' \Big|_{\substack{\theta = \theta_1 \\ \sigma_x = X_t}} = -X_t \frac{[-4F_{11} + 2(F_{66} + 2F_{12})]X_t + 2(F_2 - F_1)}{2F_{11}X_t + F_1} \quad (42)$$

but the denominator is always positive because X_c is always a negative number, i.e.,

$$2F_{11}X_t + F_1 = 2\left(-\frac{1}{X_t X_c}\right)X_t + \left(\frac{1}{X_t} + \frac{1}{X_c}\right) = \frac{1}{X_t} - \frac{1}{X_c} > 0 \quad (43)$$

Accordingly, the sign of σ_x'' is governed by the sign of the numerator, i.e.,

$$\text{sign } \sigma_x'' \Big|_{\substack{\theta = \theta_1 \\ \sigma_x = X_t}} = \text{sign}[(2F_{11} - F_{66} - 2F_{12})X_t + F_1 - F_2] \quad (44)$$

Similarly,

$$\text{sign } \sigma_x'' \Big|_{\substack{\theta = \theta_1 \\ \sigma_x = X_c}} = \text{sign}[(2F_{11} - F_{66} - 2F_{12})X_c + F_1 - F_2] \quad (45)$$

We abbreviate both Eqs. (44) and (45) by replacing X_t and X_c with X to conclude that

$$\sigma_x \Big|_{\theta = \theta_1} = 0^\circ = \begin{cases} \text{maximum if } A < 0 \\ \text{minimum if } A > 0 \end{cases} \quad (46)$$

where

$$A = (2F_{11} - F_{66} - 2F_{12})X + F_1 - F_2 \quad (47)$$

At $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$, we have two possible values of σ_x : $\sigma_x = Y_t$ and $\sigma_x = Y_c$. First,

$$\sigma_x'' \Big|_{\substack{\theta = \theta_2 \\ \sigma_x = Y_t}} = -Y_t \frac{[-4F_{22} + 2(F_{66} + 2F_{12})]Y_t + 2(F_1 - F_2)}{2F_{22}Y_t + F_2} \quad (48)$$

but

$$2F_{22}Y_t + F_2 = 2\left(-\frac{1}{Y_t Y_c}\right)Y_t + \left(\frac{1}{Y_t} + \frac{1}{Y_c}\right) = \frac{1}{Y_t} - \frac{1}{Y_c} > 0 \quad (49)$$

because Y_c is always a negative number. Thus,

$$\text{sign } \sigma_x'' \Big|_{\substack{\theta = \theta_2 \\ \sigma_x = Y_t}} = \text{sign}[(2F_{22} - F_{66} - 2F_{12})Y_t - F_1 + F_2] \quad (50)$$

Similarly,

$$\text{sign } \sigma_x'' \Big|_{\substack{\theta = \theta_2 \\ \sigma_x = Y_c}} = \text{sign}[(2F_{22} - F_{66} - 2F_{12})Y_c - F_1 + F_2] \quad (51)$$

and we conclude that

$$\sigma_x \Big|_{\theta = \theta_2 = 90^\circ} = \begin{cases} \text{maximum if } B < 0 \\ \text{minimum if } B > 0 \end{cases} \quad (52)$$

where

$$B = (2F_{22} - F_{66} - 2F_{12})Y - F_1 + F_2 \quad (53)$$

To complete the determination of the behavior of σ_x at θ_3 , we observe that if a maximum of σ_x exists at $\theta = \theta_1 = 0^\circ$ and a maximum of σ_x exists at $\theta = \theta_2 = 90^\circ$, then a minimum of σ_x must exist for some value of $\theta = \theta_3$ between 0° and 90° as in Fig. 7. Similarly, a maximum of σ_x must exist at $0 < \theta_3 < 90^\circ$ if minima of σ_x occur at $\theta = \theta_1 = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = \theta_2 = 90^\circ$. Finally, σ_x does not have a maximum between 0° and 90° if a maximum exists at 0° and a minimum exists at 90° . These various types of behavior are displayed in Fig. 7 as functions of the values of A and B which are defined in Eqs. (47) and (53).

FIGURE 7 OFF-AXIS NORMAL STRENGTH FOR TSAI-WU FAILURE CRITERION

Only the range $0^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$ is considered because of obvious symmetry for uniaxial off-axis loading. However, the meaning of maximum and minimum in Eqs. (46) and (52) must be carefully interpreted for a uniaxial off-axis compression load. There, $A > 0$ and $B > 0$ lead to an intermediate maximum of the algebraic quantity σ_x but to an intermediate minimum of the absolute value of σ_x , i.e., $|\sigma_{x_{\max}}| < |Y_c|$. This is a situation like the low shear

strength case identified for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion. Thus, we note that σ_x can be larger or smaller than Y under certain conditions (just as we found for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion).

We briefly compare the present results for the Tsai-Wu failure criterion with those for the Tsai-Hill criterion developed in the preceding section. For this purpose, consider the special case of equal strength in tension and compression and set $2F_{12} = -1/X^2$ so that the two sets of results should be the same. Then,

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{X^2} \quad F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y^2} \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{S^2} \quad (54)$$

so that

$$A = \left(\frac{2}{X^2} - \frac{1}{S^2} + \frac{1}{X^2} \right) X = \left(\frac{3}{X^2} - \frac{1}{S^2} \right) X \quad (55)$$

$$B = \left(\frac{2}{Y^2} - \frac{1}{S^2} + \frac{1}{X^2} \right) Y$$

Finally, if A and B are both positive, then the A condition is the most stringent because $X > Y$. However, this condition is

$$\frac{3}{X^2} > \frac{1}{S^2} \quad \text{or} \quad S > \frac{X}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (56)$$

which is the high shear strength condition for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion in Fig. 4. For this special case, all Tsai-Wu conditions reduce to the Tsai-Hill conditions. Thus, we can claim that the general observations for the Tsai-Hill criterion are applicable for the Tsai-Wu criterion, but are more algebraically complex.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES - OFF-AXIS NORMAL STRENGTH

We examine several common composite materials as listed in Table 1. We ignore the contribution of F_{12} in accordance with Narayanaswami and Adelman's observation that F_{12} is both difficult to measure and not a particularly important term from the standpoint of accurate strength predictions [5]. Accordingly, we work with only the data shown in Table 1. When we apply the logic of the preceding subsection, we find that, under uniaxial tension, all four materials have maxima only at 0° and minima only at 90° . That is $Y_t < \sigma_{x_{\max}} < X_t$. However, under uniaxial compression, $|X_c| > |\sigma_{x_{\max}}| > |Y_c|$ only for graphite-epoxy; for the other materials, $|\sigma_{x_{\max}}| < |Y_c|$. For the Tsai-Hill failure criterion, all four materials have the latter characteristic.

OFF-AXIS SHEAR STRENGTH

We substitute the stresses in principal material directions in terms of the off-axis shear stress τ_{xy} , Eq. (18), in the Tsai-Wu criterion, Eq. (28), to obtain

$$G\tau_{xy}^2 + H\tau_{xy} - 1 = 0 \quad (57)$$

where

$$G = \bar{G}\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta + F_{66} \quad (58)$$

$$H = \bar{H}\sin\theta\cos\theta$$

in which

$$\bar{G} = 4(F_{11} + F_{22} - F_{66} - 2F_{12}) \quad (59)$$

$$\bar{H} = 2(F_1 - F_2)$$

As with the off-axis normal strength, we use an indirect approach of differentiating Eq. (57):

$$G'\tau_{xy}^2 + 2G\tau_{xy}\tau'_{xy} + H'\tau_{xy} + H\tau'_{xy} = 0 \quad (60)$$

which at all stationary (and nonzero) values of τ_{xy} , i.e., $\tau'_{xy} = 0$, becomes

$$G'\tau_{xy} + H' = 0 \quad (61)$$

However, we avoid solution of this equation except to note that $\tau'_{xy} = 0$ at $\theta = \theta_1 = +45^\circ$, $\theta = \theta_2 = -45^\circ$, and

$$\cos\theta_3 = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{F_{66}(F_1 - F_2)^2}{(F_1 - F_2)^2\bar{G} + \bar{G}^2}}} \quad (62)$$

from which we have not been able to identify useful, concise conditions under which θ_3 exists. Thus, we proceed again to the second derivative of τ_{xy} to determine the character of σ_x .

We differentiate Eq. (60) to get:

$$G''\tau_{xy}^2 + 2G'\tau_{xy}\tau'_{xy} + 2G\tau_{xy}\tau'_{xy} + 2G(\tau'_{xy})^2 + 2G\tau_{xy}\tau''_{xy} + H''\tau_{xy} + H'\tau'_{xy} + H\tau''_{xy} = 0 \quad (63)$$

or, upon realizing that $\tau'_{xy} = 0$ and solving for τ''_{xy} , we get

$$\tau''_{xy} \Big|_{\tau'_{xy} = 0} = -\tau_{xy} \frac{G''\tau_{xy} + H''}{2G\tau_{xy} + H} \quad (64)$$

where G and H are defined in Eq. (58) and

$$\begin{aligned} G'' &= 2\bar{G}(\cos^4\theta - 6\sin^2\theta\cos^2\theta + \sin^4\theta) \\ H'' &= -4\bar{H}\sin\theta\cos\theta \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

We are now able to evaluate τ''_{xy} at the two known roots of Eq. (61).
At $\theta = +\pi/4$,

$$\tau''_{xy} \Big|_{\theta = \pi/4} = -\tau_{xy} \frac{(-2\bar{G})\tau_{xy} + (-2\bar{H})}{2G\tau_{xy} + H} \quad (66)$$

but from the solution

$$\tau_{xy} = \frac{-H \pm \sqrt{H^2 + 4G}}{2G} \quad (67)$$

of Eq. (57) by the quadratic equation, we see that

$$2G\tau_{xy} + H = \pm \sqrt{H^2 + 4G} \quad (68)$$

where the positive sign is used to obtain positive shearing stresses. We must now distinguish between a positive and a negative shearing stress in nonprincipal material directions in accordance with Jones' argument [4, pp. 61-62]. A positive shearing stress τ_{xy} is in the positive x-direction on a positive y side of a differential element (or in the positive y-direction on a positive x side of the same element). Note now that the left-hand side of Eq. (68) is the denominator of Eq. (66). Moreover, we can rewrite the numerator of Eq. (66) as

$$-4[2(F_{11} + F_{22} - 2F_{12})\tau_{xy} + F_1 - F_2 - F_{66}\tau_{xy}] \quad (69)$$

which can be shown to be

$$-4 \left[\sqrt{H^2 + 4G} - 2F_{66}\tau_{xy} \right] \quad (70)$$

Thus,

$$\tau''_{xy} \Big|_{\theta = \pi/4} = 4\tau_{xy} \left[1 - \frac{2F_{66}\tau_{xy}}{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}} \right] \quad (71)$$

where τ_{xy} is actually τ_{xy} at $\theta = \pi/4$. An identical expression is applicable

for $\theta = -\pi/4$ with the only exception being that τ_{xy} there is evaluated from Eq. (67) at $\theta = -\pi/4$.

Finally, we observe that for positive shearing stresses

$$\text{sign } \tau_{xy}'' = \text{sign} \left[1 - \frac{2F_{66}\tau_{xy}}{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}} \right] \quad (72)$$

Thus

$$\text{if } \frac{2F_{66}\tau_{xy}}{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}} > 1, \text{ then } \tau_{xy}'' < 0 \quad (73)$$

Or, upon solving for F_{66} and recognizing that $F_{66} = 1/S^2$,

$$\text{if } S^2 > \frac{2\tau_{xy}}{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}}, \text{ then } \tau_{xy}'' > 0 \quad (74)$$

We can use this test to determine the character of τ_{xy} at both $\theta = \pi/4$ and $\theta = -\pi/4$. In each case, we use a different τ_{xy} , i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } \theta = \pi/4, \quad \tau_{xy} &= \tau_{xy}^{+45} \\ \theta = -\pi/4, \quad \tau_{xy} &= \tau_{xy}^{-45} \end{aligned}$$

Then, we abbreviate Eq. (74) as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } S^2 > E, \text{ then } \tau_{xy}'' < 0 \text{ at } \theta = \pi/4 \\ \text{if } S^2 > F, \text{ then } \tau_{xy}'' > 0 \text{ at } \theta = -\pi/4 \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

where

$$E = \frac{2\tau_{xy}^{+45}}{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}} \quad F = \frac{2\tau_{xy}^{-45}}{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}} \quad (76)$$

Accordingly, having determined the character of τ_{xy} at $\pm \pi/4$, we can predict the shape of the τ_{xy} versus θ curve between those angles. For example, if $S^2 < E$ and $S^2 > F$, then the curve achieves a maximum at $+45^\circ$ and a minimum at -45° . Thus, either no stationary values occur between $+45^\circ$ and -45° or an even number (at least two) occur. The case of no intermediate stationary values is plotted schematically as curve 1 in Fig. 8. Two or more stationary values is not a likely event. However, the occurrence of one stationary value is possible (and will be shown to occur for some common materials). This situation results when maxima occur at both $+45^\circ$ and -45° as with curve 2 in Fig. 8. There, the shearing strength is lower than the value of S and the values at $\pm 45^\circ$. This situation is analogous to the low shear strength case in Fig. 4 for off-axis normal strength. The analogy to the high shear strength case in Fig. 4 is shown as curve 3 in Fig. 8. Note that the shearing strength at $+45^\circ$ is greater than that at -45° for curves 1 through 3. When the shearing strength at $+45^\circ$ is less than that at -45° , then the results typified in curves 4 through 6 result. Note that in these curves no stationary value exists at $\theta = 0^\circ$ as with the Tsai-Hill failure criterion in Fig. 6.

Let us determine whether the present analysis reduces to the result we derived for the Tsai-Hill failure criterion as Eq. (27). For the special condition of equal strengths in tension and compression, i.e., $X_t = X_c$ and

FIGURE 8 OFF-AXIS SHEAR STRENGTH FOR TSAI-WU FAILURE CRITERION

$$Y_t = Y_c,$$

$$F_1 = 0 \quad F_2 = 0 \quad F_{11} = \frac{1}{X^2} \quad F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y^2} \quad (77)$$

Moreover, we set $2F_{12} = -1/X^2$ to obtain

$$H = 0 \quad G = F_{11} + F_{22} - 2F_{12} = \frac{2Y^2 + X^2}{X^2Y^2} \quad (78)$$

Thus, from Eq. (67),

$$\tau_{xy}^{+45} = \frac{\sqrt{H^2 + 4G}}{2G} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{G}} \quad (79)$$

and from Eq. (74),

$$\text{if } S^2 > \frac{2/\sqrt{G}}{2/\sqrt{G}}, \text{ the } \tau_{xy}'' > 0 \quad (80)$$

we see that the condition for maxima and minima reduces to

$$\text{if } S > \frac{1}{\sqrt{G}}, \text{ then } \tau_{xy}'' > 0 \quad (81)$$

which because of Eq. (78) for G is exactly the condition in Eq. (27) for the Tsai-Hill criterion.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES - OFF-AXIS SHEAR STRENGTH

For the materials listed in Table 1 we have no values for the interaction strength F_{12} . However, as with the off-axis normal strength numerical examples, we can ignore F_{12} by setting it equal to zero. We make that approximation, but we also use the maximum acceptable values of F_{12} from the closed failure surface condition

$$F_{12}^2 \leq F_{11}F_{22} \quad (82)$$

expressed by Tsai and Wu [2]. Those values are, from Eq. (82),

$$F_{12} = \pm \sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}} \quad (83)$$

Irrespective of which of the three values of F_{12} used (zero or those in Eq. (83)), all four materials in Table 1 exhibit the type of behavior shown as curve 1 in Fig. 8. However, for AVCO 5505 Boron-Epoxy Pipes and Cole [6] report

$$\begin{aligned} X_t &= 188\text{ksi} & Y_t &= 9\text{ksi} & S &= 10\text{ksi} \\ X_c &= -361\text{ksi} & Y_c &= -45\text{ksi} & & \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

plus a value of $F_{12} = -.58 \times 10^{-4}(\text{ksi})^{-2}$ from which we calculate a behavior like curve 2 in Fig. 8 where, from Eq. (62), the minimum strength occurs at -21.2° . Thus, at least two of the six types of behavior depicted in Fig. 8 are shown to exist.

We are not likely to find materials of the types represented with curves 4 through 6 in Fig. 8 because compression strengths across the fibers generally exceed the tension strengths, i.e., $Y_c > Y_t$. That is, from the sketches at $+45^\circ$ and -45° in Fig. 8, we can easily appreciate that the state of principal stresses coincides with principal material directions. Moreover, at $+45^\circ$, the principal strengths are X_t and Y_c whereas at -45° , the principal strengths are X_c and Y_t . Obviously, behavior of the types depicted in curves 4 through 6 can occur for special combinations of the various strengths. However, we have not yet identified such behavior for the composite materials we have examined.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have demonstrated that fiber-reinforced composite laminae can have off-axis normal strengths that are greater than X or less than Y as well as shear strengths that are greater or less than S . Thus, we must reinterpret or emphasize that the concept of principal material directions is limited to axes of material property symmetry, not directions of largest or smallest material properties. Moreover, even material property symmetries do not exist when strengths are different in tension than in compression, as is usually the case.

The basic importance of the present results is that they expose the proper strength behavior of composite materials. By understanding how the range of values encountered for shear strengths can affect the off-axis uniaxial normal strength, for example, we are better prepared to interpret strength results for various materials and to use them properly in design applications. For example, on the basis of this work we should not expect to use a "low" shear strength composite material in applications where off-axis loading occurs without realizing that the off-axis strength can be much lower than Y , the strength perpendicular to the fibers. Moreover, when screening possible new composite materials, we can determine their off-axis strength behavior without performing off-axis tests. That is, we need use only the usual tension, compression, and shear strength measurements in principal material directions to predict the character of off-axis behavior with the equations derived in this paper.

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